
AGRO-ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION AMONG POLYTECHNIC STUDENTS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA: A STUDY UNDER THE PREMISES OF THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

Based on Theory of Planned Behavior, this study specifically examined the effect of attitude, perceived behavioural control and subjective norms on graduating students' intention to start Agro-entrepreneurship as well as investigated the moderating effect of gender on the relationship among the factors. A cross-sectional design was used to collect data from 400 Polytechnic students using the questionnaire. The results of the study demonstrated that attitude toward Agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behavioral control, and subjective norms have positive and significant effects on agro-entrepreneurship intention among the Polytechnic students and that male graduate students accept more agro-business than female students. Based on the findings, we recommended that tertiary institutions should continuously explore attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship practices; perceived behaviour control and subjective norms in engendering agro-entrepreneurship intention among the graduating students. Thus, policy makers can facilitate the promotion of Agro-entrepreneurship among students and graduating students.

Keywords: *Agro-Entrepreneurship, Planned behaviour, Entrepreneurial Environment, Agro-business, gender acceptance.*

INTRODUCTION

The increasing rate of graduate unemployment in Nigeria has drawn the attention of the policy-makers and government at all levels to create all-inclusive awareness campaign aimed at improving the socio-economic well-being of the people by indoctrinating entrepreneurial intention among students. This awareness campaign came to the fore, following the increasing rate of graduate unemployment which heretofore brew crime, banditry, kidnapping and the alike (Adeniyi, 2022). This concern, however, made the government to come up with a policy framework of inclusion of entrepreneurship education as a compulsory course for all students with effect from the 2007/2008 academic session (Aliu, 2022). Today, most tertiary institutions in Nigeria offered variegated entrepreneurship studies to arm students with entrepreneurial skills capable of changing their mental capacity, creative thinking and innovative behaviour toward agro-entrepreneurial intention. The theory of planned behavior (TPB) is a psychological theory that links beliefs to behavior and comprises three core components namely, attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. These together shape an individual's behavioral intentions. The theory posits that attitude towards behavior, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control influences entrepreneurial intention which in turn predicts Agro-entrepreneurship behavior. TPB is the immediate antecedent of a behavior. Changes in intention and actual behavior are dependent upon changes in attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

Entrepreneurial intention refers to an individual's objective to start a high-growth business and work as an entrepreneur in the future. Behavioral intention, which is the motivational factors that influence behavior (Ajzen, 1991). The stronger the intention to engage in a given behavior, the more likely it is to perform that behavior. Agro-entrepreneurship in common language can be defined as sustainable, community-oriented, directly-marketed agriculture. Sustainable agriculture refers a system-oriented approach to farming that put emphasis on the interrelationships of social, economic, and environmental. Attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control form a behavioral intention, which is the immediate antecedent of a behavior. Changes in intention and actual behavior are dependent upon changes in attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Entrepreneurial intention therefore is a disposition of becoming self-employed (Miriti, 2020). It is concerned with the re-orientation of individual perception to becoming an entrepreneur in the future. This is why Otchengco & Akiate, (2021) believed that to indoctrinate such entrepreneurial intention; attitude of the people must be structured and repositioned to accepting to venture into business. Ramuhu (2023) created an all-inclusive model that encapsulated entrepreneurial intention into three critical but notably mutually dependent in driving the people's disposition and perception toward entrepreneurial intention. The three factors among other considerations are but not limited to perceived net desirability of self-employment, the perceived feasibility of becoming self-dependent and meeting of one's socio-economic needs and expectation per-time.

Despite the entrepreneurial studies going-on in the Nigerian tertiary institutions, the attitude, behavioural control and subjective norms are still at low ebb, graduate unemployment is on the increase, crime rate, kidnapping case and banditry are skyrocketed. A number of studies according to Berlin (2022) have been carried out to examine agro-entrepreneurial intention as a leeway of promoting and enhancing graduate involvement into agro-business. Considering, the relatively increasing rate of graduate unemployment resulting from dearth of agro-entrepreneurial skills in Nigeria, studies investigating such are few. Most of the studies are western-based, hence this research aims to fill the gap by examining the agro-entrepreneurial intention among Polytechnic students in Anambra State. Specifically, the study examined the

effect of attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, determined the effect of perceived behavioural control on intention to agro-entrepreneurship, ascertained the effect of subjective Norms on intention to agro-entrepreneurship and investigated the moderating effect of gender on agro-entrepreneurship intention among the graduating Polytechnic Students in Anambra State.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

The underpinning theory of this study is Planned Behaviour which emerged as the theory of reasoned action in 1980. The theory tends to explain several dimensions through which individual could be motivated to behave or exert self-control (Abdullah and Sulaiman 2013). The key constituent to this model is behavioral intent; behavioral intentions are influenced by the attitude about the likelihood that the behavior will have the expected outcome and the subjective evaluation of the risks and benefits of that outcome. TPB is a psychological theory that links beliefs to behavior. Theory of planned behaviour has been used to predict people's responsiveness and intentions to behave in anticipated manner. This is why this theory most fit this present study, because it lays credence on the fact that attitude, behaviour and social norm dove-tailed the expected outcome. The theory maintains that three core components namely, attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, together shape an individual's behavioral intentions.

The Concept of Agro-Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurial intention is referred to as the willingness or intention to start up and engage in entrepreneurial behaviour (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt, & Ringle, 2019). The intention toward agro-business emanates from individual psychological disposition to be self-employed and independent. The idea of attaining certain heights of meeting up our socio-economic needs stir or motivate individuals to agro entrepreneurial intention of starting business in the future. The aforementioned presupposition was also shared with Makuum, (2022) who said that entrepreneurial intention is the function of perceived disposition that is governed with the desire to be self-reliance, independent and self-sufficiency. Within the operationalized dimensions of agro-entrepreneurial intention are three critical and largely directional in reinforcing the psychological perception of students' intention to agro-businesses which are outlined below: attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behavioural control and subjective norms.

Attitude toward Agro-Entrepreneurship

Attitude for innovative behaviour is the extent individuals develop good mental picture to venture into agro-entrepreneurship (Ridha, Burhanuddin, Wahyu (2017)). In order to have a very good attitude according to Jack, (2020) stems from having holistic understanding with cognate experience on agro-entrepreneurship to be able to translate that to others in creating the desired agro-entrepreneurship attitude to students. This is what made Nematoola, Davoud and Seyed (2020) to have resolved and determined that for any institution to create a convivial learning environment, their entrepreneurship studies must be equipped with necessary entrepreneurial tools or equipment to have practical insights on the need to develop good as well as positive attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship.

Subjective norms

Subjective norms refer to an individual's personal impression about how others in their immediate social circle, such as parents, relatives, and neighbors, would react to them engaged in or not engaged in a particular behavior, such as entrepreneur (Al-Jubari, 2019).

The perceived social pressures that drive people to behave in more socially acceptable habits are also referred to as the subjective norm (Soon et al., 2016). People are significantly influenced by social pressure to behave in a certain way. Students are more confident to become entrepreneurs if they have strong support from family and relatives (Ambad et al., 2016). Thus, students may seek guidance and encouragement from those around them, and their views may impact whether or not to participate in entrepreneurial action (Al-Jubari, 2019). Subjective norm has a positive and considerable influence on the intention of young entrepreneurs, according to empirical research (Al-Jubari, 2019; Ridha et al., 2017).

Perceived Behavioural Control

Perceived behavioural control is concerned with the belief system that one can behave in anticipated manner (Tharder, 2022). Though, individuals have their own value system that mold their belief system and predispose them to behave in a certain manner. To this end, a student can become an entrepreneur if he/she possesses the value system that he/she can perform credibly well as an entrepreneur. Therefore, perceived behavioural control is the perception of how easy or difficult people can behave in anticipated manner. With a positive system value, individuals are more likely to engage in agro-entrepreneurship. If the system value is such that allow for innovative behaviour, people tend to responds proactively to business. For instance, the planned behaviour theory hypothesized that individual belief system is key and central to certain behaviour.

Operational Model for the Study

The theory of planned behavior posits that attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control influences entrepreneurial intention which in turn predicts Agro-entrepreneurship behavior. Attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control form a behavioral intention, which is the immediate antecedent of a behavior. Changes in intention and actual behavior are dependent upon changes in attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. These three constructs are operationalized in this study.

FIG. 1 Three constructs of the theory of planned behavior as operationalized in the study.

METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive research design using a survey research-based method based on quantitative approach. The target population of this study comprised all final year students of

the two Polytechnics in Anambra State namely: Federal Polytechnic Oko and Anambra state Polytechnic, Mgbakwu. Federal Polytechnic Oko has approximately 1300 graduating students while Anambra State Polytechnic, Mgbakwu has approximately 200 graduating students, making it a total of 1500 graduating students. In determining the sample size for this study, the Taro Yamani (1967) formular for a finite population was applied thus.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- n = The sample size
- N = The finite population
- e = error limit (5% level of significance)
- I = Unity (constant)

Applying the formula:

$$n = \frac{1500}{1 + 1500(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1500}{3.752} = 399.78 \approx 400 \text{ Students}$$

Four hundred (400) polytechnic graduating students were sampled via cross-sectional study from the two Polytechnics in the State. In this study, therefore, the proportional stratified random sampling technique was used to select the number of students studied from each stratum since the sub- sectors are not equal. The proportional stratified random sampling technique involves the selection from the two Polytechnics in the sample from the sub-groups in proportion to the size of each sub-group in the population. Thus, we have;

$$\text{Federal Polytechnic Oko} = \frac{1300}{1500} \times 400 = 346$$

$$\text{Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu} = \frac{200}{1500} \times 400 = 54$$

Instruments used for Data Collection

The major instrument used for data collection in this study is a 31-item researcher developed questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section covers sample characteristics of the respondents (showing age, gender, program of study, practical experiences among others). The second section comprises questions in relation to the study. This consists of 25- items structured and closed ended questions, which provide fixed answers in a five-point Likert scale. The respondents were asked to express their views and levels of agreement with the statements. Five response options were given. Weights of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 respectively are assigned to the response options. Agro-Entrepreneurial intentions are measured by asking participants to rate their interest in starting/ owning their own Agro-business on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = definitely not interested, 5 =extremely interested). Out of the Four hundred copies (400) of questionnaire distributed, three hundred and seventy-four (374) filled questionnaires were returned, hence used for the analysis. Data collected were analyzed with logistic regression model.

Model Specification: Mathematically, the relationship is expressed as:

$$AEI = \beta_0 + \beta_1ATA - E + \beta_2PBC + \beta_3SN + \mu$$

Where:

AEI = Agro-Entrepreneurial Intention

ATA = Attitude toward Agro-entrepreneurship

PBC = Perceived Behaviour Control

SN = Subjective Norms

β_0 = The regression intercept (constant term)

β_1 - β_3 = Coefficients of the explanatory variables

μ = Residual or Disturbance term, which represents the composite effect of exogenous variables outside the model which were not explicitly identified in the model

RESULTS

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	AEI	ATA	PBC	SN
Mean	115.0014	201.4410	211.5512	101.2311
Std. Dev.	110.4519	118.7612	122.11672	011.8416
Sum of Sq.	261110.00	1022871.00	412990.00	381003.00
Variance	44321.110	311900.552	267541.001	22315.211
Maximum St.	3321.00	3325.00	3416.00	3340.00
Minimum St.	222.00	033.00	291.00	301.00
Observations	374	374	374	374

Source: SPSS Computation Output, 2025.

Table 1 presented basic aspect of their asymptotic properties of the descriptive statistics and their respective relationships with the predictor variables under study. It shows the mean values of the dependent and independent variables. The mean values for agro-entrepreneur intention, attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behaviour control and subjective norms were 115.0014, 201.4410, 211.5512 and 101.2311 respectively. In addition, the table also presented the descriptive results of the standard deviation indicating the degree at which it measured the dispersion in the designated values. Therefore, standard deviation measures proportionately show how the data was spread around the mean. The standard deviation for agro-entrepreneurial intention, attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behaviour control and subjective norms were 110.4519, 118.7612, 122.11672 and 011.8416. In addition, the sum of square measures how far individual measurements are from the mean. To calculate the sum of squares, we subtracted each measurement from the mean, square the difference, and then add up (sum) all the resulting measurements. The results of the sum of square were 261110.00, 1022871.00, 412990.00 and 381003.00 for agro-entrepreneur intention, attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behaviour control as well as the subjective norm respectively. The implications of high sum of square above the mean indicate a high variability on the agro-entrepreneur intention among graduating students of the Polytechnics in Anambra State.

Table 2 shows the logistic regression results of the explanatory variables. The coefficient of the constant term is 2.6671 and its related t-value is statistically significant at 5% level of significance as confirmed by t-probability (0.0000). This implies that even at zero level of implementing attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behaviour control, and subjective norms, students' agro-entrepreneurial intention will increase by 5%. Therefore, the possible increase on the students' agro-entrepreneur intention could be due to exogenous

factors outside the modeled variables as in internal validity or spuriousity. The logistic regression results indicated the effect(s) of all the explanatory variables on students' agro-entrepreneurial intention. By specification, attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship has a positive coefficient of 0.6782 and it is statistically significantly at 5% level of significant as indicated by $p < 0.0000$. This positive coefficient was also affirmed by the chi-square value of 63.01. This result strongly suggests that attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship is strong predictor of agro-entrepreneur intention. However, the flagged-off result of the coefficient implies that as the polytechnic continue to sensitize the students, such actions, will bring about a significant increase on the student's agro-entrepreneurship intention in Anambra State. The result also shows the regression coefficient of the estimated perceived behavioural control on agro-entrepreneurship intention among graduating students.

Table 2: Regression Estimates

Parameter estimates						
Term	Estimate	SE	Chi-square	Prob > chi-square	Lower CL 95%	Upper CL 95%
Intercept	2.6671	2.5511	52.44	> 0.0000	12.00	27.00
ATA	.6782	.00112	63.01	> 0.0000	17.11	26.11
PBC	.8092	.00031	67.22	> 0.0000	12.12	24.12
SN	.7336	.00122	68.11	> 0.0000	15.10	30-21

$$AEI = 0.6782_{ATA} + 0.8092_{PBC} + 0.7336_{SN}$$

Model	= Log likelihood	Df	Chi-square	Prob > chi-square
	122.10	2	223.2990	> 0.0001

Number of observation 374
 R^2 0.6932
 Restricted log-likelihood

Source: SPSS Computation Output, 2025.

The regression result reveals the coefficient of perceived behaviour control of 0.8092 and was statistically significant at 5% level of significance (0.0000). Also, the positive coefficient of perceived behaviour control logically suggests as this institution continues to engender perceived behaviour control on the students, such actions, will lead to significant increase on agro-entrepreneurship intention by 81% significantly. This result was also confirmed following the result of the chi-square value of 67.22, suggesting its strong moderating factor of agro-entrepreneurship intention. Table 2 also showed the regression coefficient of the estimated subjective norms on agro-entrepreneurship intention. The regression result presented the coefficient of Subjective Norms of 0.7336 and was statistically significant at 5% level of significance as confirmed by t-probability of 0.0000. Finally, the Model result showed log-likelihood function of 122.10 and the χ^2 of 223.299 were all significant ($p < 0.001$) suggesting that the model has a strong explanatory power. The pseudo coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) of 0.69 shows that 69% of the variation in dependent variable was collectively explained by the independent variables. This implies that the overall model

had a good fit and the explanatory variables used in the model were collectively able to explain the dependent variable

Table 3: Group Regression on Gender-Based

MALE				FEMALE		
Variables	Estimate	SE	Prob > chi-square	Estimate	SE	Prob > chi-square
ATA	.4435	.00021	> 0.0000	.0002	.2218	> 2.1200
PBC	.3871	.00117	> 0.0000	.1187	.0011	> 0.0000
SN	.7112	.00044	> 0.0000	.0051	.0032	> 0.0000

In table 3, the result of logistic regression on gender-based analysis in determining its moderating effect on agro-entrepreneurship intention among the graduating students showed that attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behaviour control and Subjective Norms had positive as well as significant effect on agro-entrepreneurship intention on the male students as opposed to female students that showed that attitude towards agro-entrepreneurship intention were insignificant. From general assessment of the result based on gender-based analysis, male students are tilted more to agro-entrepreneurship intention.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behaviour control and Subjective Norms have positive and significant effect on agro-entrepreneurship intention among graduating students of polytechnic in Anambra State. In addition, the result of logistic regression on gender-based analysis in determining its moderating effect on agro-entrepreneurship intention among the graduating students showed that attitude toward agro-entrepreneurship, perceived behaviour control and Subjective Norms had positive and significant effect on agro-entrepreneurship intention on the male students as opposed to female students. This positive effect of the aforementioned suggests that tertiary institutions should exert more efforts in utilizing the aforementioned constructs of agro-entrepreneurship intentions to fostering student intentions to venture into business.

Recommendations

1. Tertiary institutions should continue to explore the opportunities of working on the attitude of the students toward agro-entrepreneurship by sensitizing and re-orientating them.
2. Organizing entrepreneurial workshops for both staff and students will go a long way to in-built entrepreneurial capacity to venture into business.
3. Tertiary institutions should often use perceived behaviour control as working strategy in reinforcing entrepreneurship behaviour among the students. This is because students behaviour toward entrepreneurship intention could be anticipated via perceived behaviour control. Students attitude and behaviour are very vital in predicting students behaviour, therefore the duo must be used for the expected outcome.
4. Subjective Norms had a positive and significant effect on agro-entrepreneurship intention among the graduating students of Polytechnic, Anambra State and recommended that these institutions should continue to use various working strategies to stir students venture spirit into agro-business.

References

- Abdullah A.A., Sulaiman N.N. (2013). Factors that influence the interest of youths in agricultural entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(3), 1-15.
- Adeniyi, R. (2022) Phytoplankton and Nutrient Variations in the Iranian Waters of the Caspian Sea (Guilan region) during 2003–2004. *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 14(1), 231-245.
- Aliu, T.E. (2022). Entrepreneurial knowledge, personal attitudes, and entrepreneurship intentions among South African Enactus students. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 13(1–1), 152–158.
- Bazkiaei, H., Khan, N., Irshad, A., & Ahmed, A. (2021). Pathways toward entrepreneurial intention among Malaysian universities' students. *Business Process Management Journal*, 27(4), 1009–1032.
- Berlin, T. (2022). Acceptance of e-entrepreneurship by future entrepreneurs in developing countries: Case of Morocco. *Journal of Entrepreneurship: Research & Practice*, 1–10.
- Gabriel, F. (2022). Entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions: Assessing gender specific differences. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 15(4), 452–468.
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C.M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24.
- Hamiruzzaman T. H., Ahmad N., Ayob N. A. (2020). Entrepreneurial Intentions among Undergraduate Students in Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM). *Journal of Administrative Science*, 17(1), 125-139
- Miriti G. M. (2020). An exploration of entrepreneurial intentions among university students in Kenya. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 4(12), 1–9.
- Morris W., Henley A., Dowell D. (2023). Farm diversification, entrepreneurship and technology adoption: Analysis of upland farmers in wales. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 53, 132–143.
- Otchengco A. M. & Akiate Y. W. D. (2021). Entrepreneurial intentions on perceived behavioral control and personal attitude: Moderated by structural support. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 15(1), 14–25
- Ramuhu, K. (2023) Gender as a moderator between entrepreneurship intention and its predictors among university graduates in Nigeria and India. *African Journal of Business Management*, 13(18), 622–629.

- Ridha R. N., Burhanuddin B., Wahyu B. P. (2017). Entrepreneurship intention in agricultural sector of young generation in Indonesia. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 11(1), 76–89.
- Vamvaka, V., Stoforos, C., Palaskas, T., & Botsaris, C. (2020). Attitude toward entrepreneurship, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention: Dimensionality, structural relationships, and gender differences. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 9(1), 1–26.